

Supplementary Figure S6. Growth curves of WT (green circle) and $\Delta pflA$ (light grey square) in LB media grown (A) aerobically, (B) anaerobically, or (C) anaerobically supplemented with 50mM fumarate. Data represent the average and SEM for three independent biological replicates.